

CHEMISTRY

ALKYLATION OF PHENOL IN A CONTINUOUS REACTOR WITH A CATION-EXCHANGE CATALYST

Nagiyeva M.

*Institute of Petrochemical Processes named after Acad. Y.H. Mammadaliyev,
Ministry of Science and Education*

Nasrullayev I.

*Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University,
Department of Petrochemical Technology and Industrial Ecology*

Abstract

The use of catalysts is essential for carrying out important organic reactions with higher yields and efficiency. Heterogeneous catalysts have significant advantages over conventional homogeneous catalysts in terms of product separation, reuse, and regeneration. Cation-exchange catalysts are solid acid heterogeneous catalysts used in key reactions such as alkylation, etherification, olefin-ether reactions with alcohols, and alcohol dehydration to olefins or ethers. Alkylation involves the transfer of an alkyl group from one molecule to another and is one of the most crucial catalytic processes in the chemical industry, widely applied in fuel production, cleaning products, food industry, and pharmaceuticals. Various factors must be considered for the economic viability of the process. Continuous processing ensures rapid alkylation reactions. Applying pressure in alkylation reactors increases reaction rates, leading to heat buildup. Therefore, temperature control is crucial due to the exothermic nature of the reaction. When using cation-exchange catalysts, controlling the temperature is essential to prevent catalyst degradation. Different configurations and equipment can be employed to optimize heat dissipation and enhance alkylation efficiency.

Keywords: Continuous reactor, cation-exchange resin, alkylation, phenol, alkylating agent, homogenous and heterogenous catalysts.

Introduction: This study presents the results of investigating the alkylation reaction of phenol with 1-methylcyclohexene in the presence of the KU-2 catalyst.

Alkyl- and cycloalkylphenols serve as key raw materials for manufacturing high-performance coatings, pharmaceuticals, lubricants, bactericides, herbicides, and other chemicals. Recently, they have been widely used as precursors for the synthesis of oligomerization and polymerization products with next-generation catalysts. Consequently, developing catalysts for selective alkyl- and cycloalkylphenol synthesis is of growing interest to both science and industry [4, 5].

Cycloalkylation of phenol with various alkylating agents is conducted using catalysts such as aluminum phenolates, H-form KU-2 sulfonic cation exchangers, silicon-aluminum zeolites, and other acid catalysts. Continuous processes offer the advantage of producing large quantities of product in a short time. Typically, fixed-bed reactors are used in these processes, where two key parameters—catalyst particle size and temperature—must be considered.

This study focuses on investigating the catalytic reactions of phenol with 1-methylcyclohexene in a continuous pilot plant. The KU-2 cation-exchange resin (GOST 20298-74) was used as the catalyst. The catalyst was loaded into the continuous pilot reactor, and the alkylation was carried out in a liquid-phase flow reactor. The obtained alkylate was purified and analyzed using infrared (IR) and nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy [1, 2].

The effect of kinetic factors on product yield and process selectivity was examined to determine optimal

conditions for alkylation. The primary objective of conducting phenol alkylation in a continuous pilot reactor is to establish a foundation for future industrial-scale implementation. Continuous processing lowers production costs and simplifies technology. Thus, a decision was made to study the cycloalkylation of phenol with methylcyclohexene in a continuous pilot setup.

Experimental Procedure: Phenol and 1-methylcyclohexene were used as raw materials, while the KU-2 resin served as the catalyst. The physical and chemical properties of the initial components are provided in Table 1. The material balance for the alkylation reaction was calculated and documented.

In the continuous pilot setup, the mass flow rate was regulated at 2 kg/h. The process flow diagram of catalytic alkylation of phenol with 1-methylcyclohexene is shown in Figure 1.

The reaction mixture was prepared in pre-calculated ratios, and the temperature in the phenol container was stabilized at 40°C. The phenol and 1-methylcyclohexene mixture was introduced into the reactor's lower section via a mixer. After passing through the catalyst, the resulting compounds were transferred to a cooling unit and subsequently to an alkylate collection tank, followed by a distillation unit. The distillation process first separated unreacted phenol and 1-methylcyclohexene, and then the desired product was isolated under vacuum (10 mmHg).

The structure of the synthesized compound was verified using spectral analysis methods, the material balance for the process was determined, and a proposed mechanism for the alkylation of para-cresol was provided.

Figure 1: Process flow diagram of phenol alkylation with 1-methylcyclohexene: 1 – phenol vessel, 2- 1-methylcyclohexene vessel, 4 – mixer, 3,5 – pump, 6 – reactor, 7 – condenser, 8 – alkylate product vessel

At the conclusion of the experiment, the raw material supply was halted, and the product within the re-

actor was transferred to the tank. The KU-2 cation exchange catalyst was regenerated directly inside the reactor.

Table 1.

Physical and chemical properties of raw materials

Compounds	$T_{\text{melt}}, ^\circ\text{C}$	$T_{\text{boiling}}, ^\circ\text{C}$	$\rho_4^{20}(\text{g/ml})$	n_D^{20}	Molecular Mass (g/mol)
Phenol	40.5	181.7	1.034	1.224	94.113
1-methylcyclohexene	-120	110	0.81	1.45	96.17

KU-2 Catalyst Preparation for synthesis:

To convert 50 g of KU-2 cationite to its acidic form, it is placed in a column equipped with a bottom drain valve. The cationite layer is poured and then covered with a 10% HCl solution, maintaining the acid level 15-20 mm above the cationite. The valve is opened, allowing 400-500 ml of 10% HCl to flow through the column. This process is repeated until the

acid concentration in the effluent remains stable. Following acid treatment, the catalyst is rinsed with distilled water in a separating funnel until the outflow appears neutral, as determined by a methyl orange indicator [2, 3].

The structure of KU-2 catalyst is represented in below mentioned Figure 2.

Figure 2. KU-2 catalyst

The KU-2 catalyst offers the advantage of a 4,000-hour operational lifespan, while also producing alkylation products in a sufficiently pure form without the need for pre-washing with water. Additionally, it prevents olefins from undergoing isomerization, allowing

them to be reintroduced into the process without altering the alkylation conditions.

The cycloalkylation reaction of phenol with 1-methylcyclohexene in the presence of the KU-2 catalyst proceeds as illustrated in Figure 3 (see 2nd reaction, 1st reaction is with 1-methylcyclohexene).

Figure 3. The continuous unit facilitates the reaction between phenol and 1-methylcyclohexene in the presence of the KU-2 catalyst. Reactants are steadily introduced into the reactor, where the cycloalkylation process takes place under controlled conditions, ensuring continuous product formation and separation.

To achieve a high yield and selectivity of 2-(1-Methylcyclohexyl)-phenol, the influence of reaction temperature, the molar ratio of the initial components, and volume velocity on the cycloalkylation reaction pathway was investigated.

To optimize yield and selectivity:

- The reaction temperature was examined within the range of 80–140°C.
- The molar ratio of phenol to 1-methylcyclohexene was varied from 1:2 to 2:1.
- The volume velocity was analyzed within the range of 0.2–1.0 h⁻¹

Figure 4 (a, b, c) illustrates the dependence of yield (1) and selectivity (2) of 2-(1-Methylcyclohexyl)-phenol on temperature (a), the molar ratio of phenol to 1-methylcyclohexene (b), and volume velocity (c).

Figure 4-a shows that, within the temperature range of 80–100°C, the yield of the target product in the cycloalkylation reaction between phenol and 1-methylcyclohexene ranges from 36% to 48.3%, while selectivity increases from 71.2% to 80.3%. These values are not optimal for cycloalkylation reactions. The low yield of the reaction product is explained by the insufficient energy of the initial components in the charge, preventing the full progression of the reaction. The low selectivity for the target product is due to the formation of cyclohexylphenyl ethers at lower temperatures. When the reaction temperature is raised to 120°C, the yield of

the target product increases to 58.7%, and selectivity rises to 85.6%. Further increasing the temperature results in a higher yield of the target product, reaching 61.6%, but selectivity drops to 78.5%. This decline is due to the formation of undesirable by-products as the temperature increases.

The effect of the molar ratio of the initial components on the yield and selectivity of 2-(1-methylcyclohexyl)-phenol is also significant. Figure 4-b shows that when the molar ratio of 1-methylcyclohexene in the reaction mixture is increased, the yield of the target product is 38.9% (for phenol), and selectivity is 69.4%. The

low yield and selectivity are attributed to the increased return of 1-methylcyclohexene and the higher formation of 2,6-dimethylcyclohexyl-4-methylphenol.

The figure illustrates that a molar ratio of phenol to 1-methylcyclohexene of 1:1 results in a high yield and selectivity for the target product. Under these conditions, the yield of 2-(1-Methylcyclohexyl)-phenol is 58.7%, and the selectivity is 85.6%. When the amount of phenol is doubled, the yield of the target product increases to 63.6%, and the selectivity rises to 90.4%. However, increasing the amount of phenol to achieve higher yield and selectivity is not considered economically or technologically efficient.

Figure 2 indicates that optimal yield and selectivity for the target product can be achieved at a volume flow rate of 0.5 h⁻¹ for the component mixture. The desired results are not attained at other volume flow rates.

Based on the experimental results, the optimal conditions for the cycloalkylation reaction of phenol with 1-methylcyclohexene in the presence of the KU-2 catalyst in a continuously operating pilot plant are as follows:

- Temperature: 120°C
- Molar ratio of phenol to 1-methylcyclohexene: 1:1
- Volume flow rate: 0.5 h⁻¹

Under these conditions, the yield of 2-(1-Methylcyclohexyl)-phenol is 58.7%, and the selectivity of the target product is 85.7%. The material balance to produce 2-(1-Methylcyclohexyl)-phenol in a continuously operating pilot plant with the KU-2 catalyst has been calculated. The results are provided below:

Table 2.

Final mass balance table

I. Cycloalkylation	mass,g	%
Raw materials:		
1) Phenol	94,10	52.8
2) 1- methylcyclohexene	96.0	47.2
Total:	204.0	100.0
Product:		
–Alkylate	200.0	98.6
Loss	4.0	1.4
Total:	204.0	100.0
II. Rektifikasiya		
Götürülən:		
– Alkilat	200.0	100.0
Total:	200.0	100.0
Əldə olunan:		
1) Recycled 1- methylcyclohexene	27.8	13.9
2) Recycled phenol	30.8	15.4
3) 2-(1-methylcyclohexyl)-phenol	117.9	58.7
4) 2,6-di-(1-methylcyclohexyl)-phenol	14.6	7.3
5) Qalan	6.2	3.1
Loss	4.3	2.2
Total:	200.0	100.0

The material balance of the process reveals that, after rectifying the alkylate obtained from the alkylation reaction, 117.9 g of the target product, 14.6 g of 2,6-disubstituted phenol, and 6.2 g of resin-like residue were produced. This results in a 58.7% yield for the target product and a selectivity of 85.7%.

Result: As a result, studies were conducted on the catalytic alkylation of phenol with 1-methylcyclohexene in the presence of the KU-2 cationite catalyst in a continuously operating pilot plant. To determine the optimal conditions for achieving the highest yield and selectivity of the target product, the effects of various kinetic parameters (temperature, molar ratio of starting components, and volume rate) on the reaction were investigated. The research demonstrated that under optimal conditions (120°C temperature, molar ratio of phenol to 1-methylcyclohexene of 1:1, volume rate of 0.5 h⁻¹), the yield of the target product, 2-(1-Methylcyclohexyl)-phenol, was 58.7% (based on the phenol used), and the selectivity of the process was 85.7% (based on the target product). The structure of the synthesized

compound was confirmed through spectral analysis methods, and the material balance of the process was calculated.

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